

Paper 2

A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF E-COMMERCE ON OFFLINE RETAIL BUSINESS

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Abstract:

E-commerce is one of the greatest inventions in this decade, it took the physical market into the virtual world with the help of the internet by offering more convenience logistics, easy return and variety of stocks, in the last five years Indian e-commerce industry has seen significant growth with the emergence of many online retailers, in the same period many offline retailers have suffered much loss on this background this study has been undertaken to know which type of offline retailers has suffered much impact among electronic shop, clothing shop, pharmacy, book shop, and provision store, electronics and clothing shop had much impact so far and all retailers feel the need of adopting e-commerce to their business.

Keywords: E-commerce, Retail business, offline, customer attraction.

1. Introduction

The concept of e-commerce started 40 years ago with electronic data interchange and teleshopping as a tool to do business, in last 15 years' development in technology helped e-commerce to include a number of features, today it is one of the effective ways of doing business. E-commerce is described as a commercial transaction which is conducted through the internet, like marketing, promotion, communication, order processing, bills payment, queries, it can be adapted to all models of business like B2B, B2C, C2B etc., Some companies adopted this invention and took the physical market into the virtual world by offering more convenience, logistics, easy return, varieties of stocks and a better shopping experience and made a traditional way of doing business outdated, this led to closure of many offline retail businesses when they couldn't adapt to a new trend. This article mainly discusses two things, they are about the impact of e-commerce on offline retail business and strategies that retailers have to adopt in order to compete with a new trend.

2. Recent Trends in E-commerce Industry

- The Indian e-commerce market has reached \$50 billion in 2018 from \$39 billion in 2017 and it is expected to grow as the world's second largest e-commerce market by 2034.
- Internet users in India are expected to reach 829 million in 2021 from 429.23 million in 2017, raising internet users is expected to boost the growth of e-commerce.
- In the online retail market electronics is currently the largest segment with 47% market share, followed by clothing 31%, home and furnishing 8%, books 7%, personal care 2%, baby products 2% and others 3%.
- Offline retailers share in the total retail market is expected to go down to 95% in 2020 from 97.5% in 2016, in the same period online retail is expected to grow from 2.5% to 5%.

- The Indian government has allowed the online sale of drugs by forming the e-pharmacy draft on 28th August 2018.
- The government has banned online retailers from making big and exclusive offers from 1st February 2019 in order to balance competition between offline retailers.

3. Impact of E-commerce on Offline Retail Business.

The emergence of e-commerce can be considered as a boon to traditional retail business when they know how to adapt and make use of it when they don't know how to adopt it and cope up with the new trend it will become difficult for them to succeed in this generation. It helps business in operating efficiently as well as effectively in reaching customers located thousands of miles away within minutes, most of the business process can be performed effortlessly through it, launching new products all over the world with low cost at same time is possible through it, so far it has helped many traditional retailers to expand their business, at the same time it also had negative impact others offline retailers.

4. Review of Literature

Menal (2017) "Study on E-commerce and its impact on retailers in India" studies types of markets and impact of e-commerce on retailers in India, Major advantages that e-commerce has over retailers are promotion of products, customer service, brand image, advertisement, customization, order-making process, customer values, all these factors affected retailers in decreased turnover, profit margin and increased customer demands like discounts, returns, home delivery etc., and there is a need for making more advertisement and offers by retailers, which are difficult to fulfill by them.

Amithshah (2015) "A study on the impact of online shopping upon retail trade business" Majority of retailers agree that there is a decrease in average turnover and profit margin in the last 3 years and many tried to regain customer attraction by giving offers, discounts, and after-sales service, and they didn't keep more variety of stocks rather kept the best stock to affect more sales, retailers have to provide better quality products with fair price and good consumer satisfaction in order to regain profits.

Kiran (2017) "Impact of e-commerce on global business and opportunities- a conceptual study" easy access to internet supports e-commerce growth, e-commerce will show tremendous support in the promotion of global business, it has both positive and negative impact on employment where it creates new type of jobs like web designing, computer engineering, system analyst and also employs creative people, artists, designers for making web content more attractive, automation in e-commerce in self-service facilities will reduce traditional employment opportunities like administration and back-office functions.

5. Research Gap

Earlier many studies were conducted regarding the impact of e-commerce on whole employment and retail business, and some suggested that e-commerce will have a negative impact on whole offline retail business and some said it will not have a negative impact on the whole traditional retail market, to clear these confusions this study was conducted. This study aims at knowing which kind of traditional retail business is more affected and which are less affected.

6. The problem of the Offline Retailers

- Some big online retail companies are giving very tough competition to offline retailers.

- In the last three years' easy access to the internet gave a boost to online retailer's growth.
- Big discounts and low price products offered by online retailers is a threat to the offline retailer's growth.
- Many traditional retailers don't have adequate skills and resources needed to adopt e-commerce.
- Many kinds of traditional retailers already have disappeared like record shops etc.

7. Objectives of the Study

1. To evaluate the impact of e-commerce on offline retail business.
2. To offer suggestions to develop the retail business in order to meet a new kind of customer needs.

8. Research Methodology

For this study, Shimoga district in the Karnataka state of India is selected as an area of study, primary data are collected from the respondents using structured questionnaire, ten respondents were selected each from the five types of retail business namely electronic appliances shop, cloth shop, pharmacy, books shop, and provision store. Further data required are collected from articles, journals, and reports. All the data's collected were analyzed using statistical tools and techniques and chi-square test.

9. Limitations of the Study

- 1) Only five types of offline retail shops were compared to know the impact of e-commerce on offline retail business.
- 2) A sample size of each type of shop is just 10 respondents.

10. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Impact of Online Retailers and E-commerce on Offline Retail Business

Particulars	Electronic gadgets shop		Clothing shop		Pharmacy		Books shop		Provision store	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Is there a decrease in average number of customers in last 3 years.	8	2	7	3	4	6	5	5	3	7
Is there a decrease in average profit margin in last 3 years.	5	5	6	4	3	7	3	7	4	6
Do you think big online retailers has caused loss to your business in the last 3 years?	9	1	8	2	4	6	6	4	3	7
Can you offer big discounts like online retailers.	2	8	5	5	4	6	3	7	4	6
Have you tried any strategies to compete with online retails.	4	6	6	4	3	7	2	8	1	9
Do you think online retailers are a big threat to your business in the future?	9	1	7	3	8	2	8	2	4	6

Do you feel the need of adopting e-commerce to your business.	8	2	9	1	6	4	7	3	5	5
Are you aware of the online market place offered by Flipkart, Amazon, and others?	8	2	7	3	7	3	6	4	4	6
Do you have the adequate skills needed to adopt e-commerce to your business?	7	3	3	7	3	7	4	6	2	8
Do you think adopting e-commerce will help the growth of your business.	7	3	8	2	5	5	8	2	6	4

Source: Field survey.

Data analysis of the respondents indicate that, electronic and cloth shops has witnessed much decrease in average profit margin and customers in the last 3 years, and they both mainly considers online retailers are reason for their cause, all type of shops feel the need of adopting e-commerce to their business but many of them are unaware of online market place offered by online retail brokers, except electronic shop owners majority of shop owners lack adequate skills and knowledge needed to adopt e-commerce, and many agree that adopting e-commerce will help in the growth of their business.

Table 2: Need for adopting E-commerce to the traditional Retail Business

Ho: There is no need to adopt e-commerce to the retail business.

H1: There is a need for adopting e-commerce to the retail business.

Particulars	Observed (O)	Expected (E)	O-E	(O-E) ²
Yes	35	27	8	64
No	15	23	-8	64
n = 2	50	50		128
				$\sum(O-E)^2$

Source: Field Survey.

$$E = \sum x/n = 50/2 = 25$$

$$\text{Degree of Freedom} = n-1 (2-1) = 1$$

$$X^2 = \sum(O-E)^2/E$$

$$X^2 = 128/25 = 5.12$$

Significance level= 5%

Table Value of chi square = 3.841

The primary data from the respondents were collected and analyzed and a hypothesis has been framed to test whether there is a need for adopting e-commerce among traditional retailers by using chi-square test, and the computed value of chi-square is 5.12 and the critical value is 3.84 by taking a degree of freedom 1 (n-1 i.e. 2-1) at 5% significance level. As the computed value 5.12 is greater than table value 3.84, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis has been accepted which shows that there is a need for adopting e-commerce among traditional retailers.

11. Major Findings of the Study

- The emergence of e-commerce helped the growth of logistics and other related business and affected some business like print publication and others.

- All type of offline retail shops is not affected, electronic shop and clothing shops are more affected and others are less affected.
- Provision stores and other shops which sell daily household goods and perishable goods are not affected by e-commerce because people are not preferring e-commerce to buy everything.
- Traditional offline retail shops are unable to compete with online retailers in terms of pricing, offers, discounts, return and exchange offers.
- Majority of offline retail shops feel the need of adopting e-commerce to their business.
- Awareness level and skills needed to adopt e-commerce to the business among the traditional retailers is low.
- Pharmacies didn't have much impact in the past but they think government allowing e-pharmacy will have a negative impact on them in the future.

Suggestions

- Offline retailers have to adopt e-commerce in their business in order to grow in the present generation.
- **Adopting online and offline customer experience:** Many small offline retailers are not equipped with enough resource and skills to adopt e-commerce, so they can start adopting basics e-commerce features like
 - Adopting credit, debit card and mobile payment options.
 - Adopting teleshopping, it is a very easy way of reaching more customer by letting the customer order through phone and personally delivering those products to their home.
 - Storing customers purchase data and providing recommendations and discounts when they visit again.
 - Sending offers and information about the arrival of new products through SMS.
 - Analyzing new trends and strategies used by online retailers and trying to adopt it.
- **Partnering with online retail brokers:** There are a number of online retail brokers websites available nowadays which allow anyone to sell products online without setting up of their own store or website, terms and conditions of online market place vary between one to another, offline retailers can join multiple online market place and sell their products to wider areas, benefits of joining online market place are as follows.
 - Access, advertising and promoting products to a wider area is possible with very less cost.
 - Can sell directly to customers through online or sell in bulk quantity to the retail brokers.
 - The separate platform is available to launch new products and handmade goods.
 - Easy access to convenient logistics support.
 - Some online retail brokers provide storage and credit facility.

12. Conclusion

The way of doing business has been changed by the emergence of e-commerce, it has seen tremendous growth in the last few years in the same period some traditional retailers suffered slowdown in their business because they were unable to keep up with new trend, they should not be left out rather they should be brought up by making them aware of e-commerce and helping them in joining online market place where they can easily expand their business to the online world.

References

1. Menal Dahiya (2017) “Study on e-commerce and its impact on market and retailers in India” Research India publications, ISSN 0973-6107, Vol 10.
2. Amithshah (2015) “A study on the impact of online shopping upon retail trade business” IOSR journal of business and management, ISSN: 2319-7668
3. Dr. Kiran S Nair (2017 “Impact of e-commerce on global business and opportunities- A conceptual study” IJAEMR, ISSN: 2436-3676, Vol. 2, Issue 2.
4. Steve Burt, Leigh Sparks (2003) “E-commerce and the retail process: A review”, Journal of retailing and consumer service, 10 (2003), 275-286.
5. www.ibef.org